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ZABEZPIECZENIE PRAWNE PRZYJĘCIA DECYZJI ZARZĄDCZYCH PRZEZ KIEROWNIKÓW JEDNOSTEK POLICJI NARODOWEJ UKRAINY

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Streszczenie. Konieczność i niezbędność podejmowania decyzji zarządczych jest główną funkcją aktywności zawodowej szefów organów i jednostek Policji Narodowej Ukrainy. Ujawnienie istoty wsparcia prawnego przy podejmowaniu przez kierowników decyzji zarządczych pozwoli na terminowe korygowanie i ukierunkowanie działalności kierowników w celu zwiększenia efektywności i skuteczności ich zarządzania. Osiągnąć skuteczność wsparcia prawnego przy podejmowaniu decyzji zarządczych przez kierowników w jednostkach Policji Narodowej Ukrainy można zapewnić w przypadku harmonizacji wymagań przepisów zewnętrznych i wewnętrznych. Przygotowywanie i przyjmowanie aktów prawnych przez Policję Narodową jest jedną z głównych procedur w działalności wykonawczej i nadzorczej jej kierowników. Opracowywanie i wdrażanie aktów prawnych ma na celu zapewnienie prawidłowego wykonywania obowiązującego prawa w działalności Policji, określenie specyfiki realizacji norm prawnych oraz poprawę skuteczności działań w zakresie egzekwowania prawa.

Słowa kluczowe: działalność egzekucyjna, kierownicy, jednostki Policji Narodowej Ukrainy, wsparcie prawne, zewnętrzna baza normatywna, wewnętrzna baza normatywna, podejmowanie decyzji zarządczych, skuteczność działalności zarządczej.

LEGAL PROVIDING APPROVAL OF MANAGEMENT DECISIONS BY HEADS OF DEPARTMENTS IN NATIONAL POLICE OF UKRAINE

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Abstract. The necessity managerial decision-making is explained by the fact that exactly decision-making represents the main function of professional activity of epy heads of organs and units of the National Police of Ukraine. The disclosure of the essence of legal support while managerial decision-making allow timely correct and direct the activities of managers in order to increase the efficiency and effectiveness of management. Achievement of efficiency is possible due to the harmonization of external and internal regulations of legal acts. The preparation and adoption of legal acts by the National Police is one of the main procedures in the executive and supervisory activities of its leaders. The development and implementation of legal acts are intended to ensure the proper implementation of the current legislation in Police activity, to determine the peculiarities of the implementation of legal norms and to increase the effectiveness of all law enforcement activity.

Key words: law enforcement activity, units of the National Police of Ukraine, legal support, external normative base, internal normative base, managerial decision-making, effectiveness of management activity.

ПРАВОВЕ ЗАБЕЗПЕЧЕННЯ ПРИЙНЯТТЯ УПРАВЛІНСЬКИХ РІШЕНЬ КЕРІВНИКАМИ ПІДРОЗДІЛІВ НАЦІОНАЛЬНОЇ ПОЛІЦІЇ УКРАЇНИ

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Анотація. Необхідність і обов'язковість прийняття управлінських рішень є головною функцією професійної діяльності керівників органів і підрозділів Національної поліції України. Розкриття суті правового забезпечення при прийнятті управлінських рішень керівником дасть змогу вчасно корегувати та спрямовувати діяльність керівників з метою підвищення ефективності та результативності їх управління. Досягти ефективності правового забезпечення прийняття управлінських рішень керівниками в підрозділах Національної поліції України можна за умови узгодженості приписів зовнішніх та внутрішньовідомчих нормативно-правових актів. Підготовка та прийняття правових актів Національною поліцією є одними з основних процедур у виконавчо-розпорядчій діяльності її керівників. Розробка та реалізація правових актів покликані забезпечити належне виконання чинного законодавства в діяльності поліції, визначити особливості реалізації правових норм та покращити ефективність правоохоронної діяльності.

Ключові слова: правоохоронна діяльність, керівники, підрозділи Національної поліції України, правове забезпечення, зовнішня нормативна база, внутрішньовідомча нормативна база, прийняття управлінських рішень, ефективність управлінської діяльності.

Introduction.

The creation of the National Police of Ukraine on July 2, 2015, required the resolution of many issues related to the provision of its activities with the necessary regulatory framework, material, financial, human resources and other resources. There was also an urgent need to review the basic principles of police activity, to form new approaches to the definition of tasks, functions, principles, powers of the newly created body, as well as to increase the effectiveness of its activities.

One of the important factors that influence the effectiveness of the functioning of the units of the National Police of Ukraine is the management of their managers. Increasing the efficiency of managerial labor is a major measure to improve the overall mechanism for managing labor resources. The head ensures the rights of the unit, combining the interests of society and employees of the team, manages the social processes of work of all its members, ensures the integrity and systematic nature of the joint activities of the team under its control.

Among all areas of professional activity of heads of units of the National Police of Ukraine, the process of making managerial decisions takes the leading place: their development, implementation and control over implementation. The necessity and obligation to make a management decision is the main function of the professional management of the heads of bodies and units of the National Police of Ukraine. And since the principle of legality permeates everything that the head does, so understanding the features of legal support when making managerial decisions is extremely important for the success, professionalism and skill in the art of management.

Thus, law enforcement, which is accompanied by the adoption of numerous managerial decisions, is connected with the realization of the rights, freedoms and legal interests of individuals and legal entities, therefore the problems of legal provision of

management decisions in the departments of the National Police of Ukraine are very relevant.

Different aspects of the issues of making managerial decisions were investigated in the writings of VB Averyanov, O. F. Andryko, G. V. Atamanchuk, O. M. Bandurka, V. M. Bevzenka, A. I. Bezpalova, Yu. P. Bityak, V. M. Garashchuk, S. M. Gusarova, A. V. Jafarova, T. E. Kaganovskaya, R. A. Kalyuzhnyj, V. K. Kolpakova, V. V. Kopeichikova, V. O. Kryvolapchuka, O. V. Kuzmenko, A. M. Kulish, K. B. Levchenko, D. M. Lukyanets, A. I. Mykolenko, A. M. Muzychuk, V. I. Olefira, A. I. Ostapenko, VF Opryshka, A. M. Podolyaki, R. A. Serbin, O. Yu. Sinyavskaya, V. V. Sokurenko, S. G. Stetsenko, M. M. Tischenko, V. M. Shapoval al. The works of these scholars have revealed the main characteristics, components, requirements for managerial decisions, features of the process of preparation, implementation and control. However, the peculiarities of legal support for making managerial decisions by the heads of the National Police of Ukraine are not yet fully disclosed in our opinion.

An assessment of the effectiveness of any unit of the National Police of Ukraine is closely linked with the assessment of the professional activities of its head. Therefore, the purpose of the paper is to disclose legal support when making managerial decisions by the manager, which will enable them to timely correct and direct the activities of managers in order to increase the efficiency and effectiveness of their management.

1. The normative legal basis of the activities of the heads of the units of the National Police in Ukraine for the adoption of managerial decisions.

In the theory of management under the decision means a compulsory implementation of the socially necessary action of the will of the subject of governance, associated with the choice of purpose, ways and means of achieving it and the definition of performers. Management decision is an initial and fundamental point in the organization of the activities of each manager, because it is the main content of the management process (Management by the bodies of the National Police of Ukraine, 2017, pp. 174-175).

In the narrow sense of decision-making - this is the choice of the best solution from many alternatives. In the broader sense, decision making is identified with the whole process of management, and therefore the concept of decision-making covers their development, implementation, as well as control and analysis of the results of their implementation (Managed by the bodies of the National Police of Ukraine, 2017, pp. 169-170).

The quality of managerial decisions determines the whole course of the management process, the final results of law enforcement activities. Every practical operation of the police unit, whatever it may be (in the course of a search, detaining the suspect, sending information, an act of permission or prohibition) begins with the adoption of a decision that provides for a continuous chain of measures for its implementation. The diversity of managerial decisions that are made at different levels of management of the heads of the police units must meet certain general requirements:

- managerial decisions must be reasonable, objective, take into account all the peculiarities of the situation, meet the specific conditions, objectives and opportunities for achieving them;

- management decisions must comply with the requirements of legislative acts, orders of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, instructions and guidelines;

- managerial decisions must be taken within the competence of the subject of management, that is, to conform to the functional duties of the official who accepts them;

- Management decisions must be timely: delayed decisions, like premature, reduce the effectiveness of management and can lead to grave consequences;

- the managerial decision in the police departments is always policy-oriented, imperious and binding on everyone to whom it is addressed; execution of the decision is guaranteed by the rules of law, and in cases of necessity may be ensured by coercive measures;

- the management decision in the police units is taken unilaterally, even if it is the result of a collective discussion or the result of the agreement between the various subjects of management;

- management decision establishes mandatory rules of conduct or regulates individual management relationships; it can apply to the entire team or its individual members;

- managerial decision is the result of creative work; it requires a scientific approach, must be concise and consistent, understandable to the performer and not contradict the previously adopted decision or exclude them;

- the administrative decision in the police organs is taken in the established procedural order, which is regulated by the relevant normative acts (*Management by the bodies of the National Police of Ukraine, 2017, pp. 170-171*).

Managerial decision is the initial and fundamental point in the organization of each manager's activity, as it is the main content of the management process. The need for development and decision-making is conditioned by the presence of problems related to professional activity, ie, such theoretical issues or practical situations, for solving which it is necessary to carry out a number of actions both to actors and objects of management.

The administrative decision in the police units is based on laws and regulations, an analysis and assessment of the operational situation, the act of the respective head of the unit of the National Police of Ukraine. This act, which contains the statement of objectives, justification of their means of implementation, is adopted in accordance with the established procedure and ensures organizational sustainability and improvement of the activities of police units in carrying out tasks for ensuring the protection of human rights and freedoms, the interests of society and the state, combating crime, maintaining public security and order, as well as the provision of police services (*Office of the National Police of Ukraine, 2017, pp. 175*).

Legal support in making managerial decisions by the heads of the departments of the National Police of Ukraine is considered by us in connection with the implementation of the tasks set before the law-enforcement system for the protection of the rights, freedoms and legal interests of individuals and legal entities, the interests of society and the state from illegal encroachment, the fight against offenses, public order protection, public safety - on the one hand, and as a means of organizing, providing and coordinating the implementation of these tasks - from another one. Legal norms provide modeling of the procedure for making managerial decisions in the police, its valuation and formalization.

As G.V. Atamanchuk notes, the legal support of any activity, including the managerial inherent unity of sociological, normative and practical aspects (Atamanchuk,

2000, p. 68). The sociological content of legal provision consists in the fact that it only begins when it has a social need, that is, it is necessary to regulate one or another aspect of social relations, or vice versa cancel such regulation. Normative aspect of legal provision appears, as development and legal (in acts of state bodies) consolidation (setting) of the rules (rules) of human behavior and conduct socially significant cases. The practical aspect of legal provision is the real application of legal norms in public practice. The presence of this aspect requires awareness of the fact that any norm is worthless if its implementation is not provided by organizational and state structures. Thus, the presented aspects of legal support are interdependent, that is, those that are in constant interaction with each other. And the absence or inappropriate implementation of any of them can lead to the destruction of the entire system of legal provision of any socially useful activity (Atamanchuk, 2000, pp. 69-70).

In general, the system of legal support for the adoption of managerial decisions by the heads of units of the National Police of Ukraine is a set of laws and by-laws that create the legal framework for their functioning. Hence, the entire regulatory framework that managers should take into account when making managerial decisions can be divided into external, which is formally created outside the departments of the National Police, but the creation of which law enforcement bodies have a direct relationship, directly developing or participating in the development of projects of one or another normative acts, and the internal normative base, that is, the legal acts adopted by the police. The peculiarity of the legal provision of management decisions at the National Police is that the latter are endowed with the right of departmental rulemaking, the result of which is the adoption of orders, instructions, instructions, orders, etc., which are some types of administrative decisions, in particular legal ones, and can be both normative and individual (Konoplyov, 2006, p. 101).

Consequently, the normative legal basis for the activities of the heads of the National Police units of Ukraine regarding the adoption of administrative decisions is: the Constitution of Ukraine, international treaties, laws of Ukraine, decrees of the President of Ukraine, legal acts of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, acts of the Ministry of Internal Affairs and the National Police of Ukraine. other subordinate (departmental) acts taken within the limits of their authority and in accordance with the Constitution of Ukraine and laws of Ukraine, as well as acts of individual action, issued on the basis of specific legal norms (individual regulation).

2. External normative base when making managerial decisions by managers.

The Constitution of Ukraine forms the basis of the system and content of all sources of law in our state. In addition, it is the basis for the further development of Ukraine's law enforcement legislation, and, based on its provisions, all other normative acts regulating the activities of the police authorities of Ukraine are adopted. In the course of law enforcement activities, police units are guided by the rule of law principle enshrined in Article 3 of the Constitution of Ukraine, according to which a person, his rights and freedoms are recognized as the highest values and determine the content and direction of the state's activities. In carrying out their tasks, the police units ensure the observance of human rights and freedoms guaranteed by Section II of the Constitution of Ukraine (Constitution of Ukraine, 1996).

To understand the meaning of the basic law in legal provision of managerial decisions by heads of police, it is that it plays a leading role in limiting the unlawful encroachment on the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of individuals and legal

entities. The Constitution is at the top of the hierarchy of sources of law; it must necessarily meet all the regulations without exception. Being the highest act of legal force, the Constitution of Ukraine is an element of the national system of legislation. It is not passed beyond the current law, and at the same time is a specific legislative act. Its norms are of a primitive nature, they have the highest stability, the highest legal force (Commentary on the Constitution of Ukraine, 1996, p. 40).

But it should be noted that the Constitution is not able to regulate all aspects of public life. Therefore, in legal provision of managerial decisions, heads of units of the National Police have a significant place in international treaties, laws that are adopted in a special manner by regulations that directly reflect the national will and have a higher (after the Constitution) legal force. The objective need to ensure that the main issues of the adoption of managerial decisions in the police are regulated by laws, is determined by the fact that they concern a large number of individuals and legal entities, supervision and control of which activities are entrusted to law enforcement agencies.

In accordance with Article 9 of the Constitution of Ukraine, current international treaties, the consent of which is binding on the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, is part of the national legislation of Ukraine (Constitution of Ukraine, 1996). According to the provisions of the Law of Ukraine "On National Police", in its activities it is guided by international treaties of Ukraine, the consent of which is binding on the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, while in carrying out its tasks, the police ensure observance of human rights and freedoms guaranteed by the Constitution and laws of Ukraine, as well as international treaties of Ukraine, the consent of which is binding on the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, and promotes their implementation (Law of Ukraine "On National Police", 2015).

Based on the foregoing, the heads of the units of the National Police of Ukraine should be classified into international normative legal acts, which should be guided by the adoption of management decisions: the Universal Declaration of Human Rights of 10.12.1948; The Declaration on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination of 20.11.1963; International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights dated December 16, 1966; The Declaration on the Protection of All Persons from Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment of December 9, 1975; The Code of Conduct of Officials in Support of Law and Order of 17.12.1979; Basic principles of the use of force and firearms by law enforcement officials, adopted by the UN Resolution of 07.09.1990; European Code of Police Ethics of 19.09.2001 (Policy and Administration Police in Questions and Answers, 2017, p. 20). The international treaties that constitute the basis for making managerial decisions by heads of units of the National Police must include those whose legal assistance in criminal matters is the subject of which define the conceptual principles of protection and protection of the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of a person in the state, determine the bases and permissible limits law enforcement activities of the police, etc.

Among the basic laws of Ukraine that regulate the external and internal activities of police units and which managers should take into account when making managerial decisions, it should first of all be noted: Code of Ukraine on Administrative Offenses of December 07, 1984 (with amendments and additions); Labor Code of Ukraine of 10.12.1971 (as amended); Law of Ukraine "On administrative supervision of persons released from places of imprisonment" of 01.12.1994 (with amendments and supplements); Law of Ukraine "On Citizens' Appeal" of 02.10.1996 (with amendments

and supplements); The Law of Ukraine "On Prevention of Corruption" of 14.10.2014 (with amendments and additions); The Law of Ukraine "On National Police" dated 02.07.2015 (with amendments and additions) (Police Administration in Questions and Answers, 2017, pp. 17-18).

The secondary forms of legal support for the adoption of management decisions by the heads of units of the National Police are regulatory acts issued by the subjects of executive power and ensure the effectiveness of constitutional and legislative norms. Yes, the President of Ukraine, in pursuance of the assigned powers, issues decrees and orders aimed at improving the activities of the units of the National Police in making managerial decisions. Examples of such acts include the following: Decree of the President of Ukraine "On the list of positions that may be replaced by police officers in state bodies, institutions and organizations" of 09.12.2015; Decree of the President of Ukraine "On the Symbols of the National Police of Ukraine" dated 09.12.2015; Decree of the President of Ukraine "On the Day of the National Police of Ukraine" dated 09.12.2015 (Administrative Activities of the Police in Questions and Answers, 2017, p. 18).

An important place in the system of legal acts, which form the basis of legal support for the adoption of management decisions in the departments of the National Police, occupy the normative and individual legal acts of the Cabinet of Ministers as the supreme body in the system of executive power. According to the Law of Ukraine "On the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine" of 27.02.2014, its main tasks include the implementation of measures to ensure the defense capability and national security of Ukraine, public order, the fight against crime, the liquidation of the consequences of emergencies (Law of Ukraine "On the Cabinet of Ministers Ukraine", 2014).

The Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine directs and coordinates the work of ministries and other central executive authorities that ensure the implementation of state policy in relevant spheres of public and public life, the implementation of the Constitution and laws of Ukraine, acts of the President of Ukraine, and the observance of human and civil rights and freedoms.

The acts of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, which regulate the activities of the units of the National Police and influence the adoption of management decisions by their leaders, include the following: Road Traffic Law of 10.10.2001; Regulations on single officers from 30.09.2015; Regulations on the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine dated October 28, 2015; Regulations on the National Police of Ukraine dated October 28, 2015; The provision on the provision of cash for police officers seconded to state bodies, institutions and organizations as of 04.11.2015 (Policy and Administration of Police in Questions and Answers, 2017, pp. 18-19).

The peculiarity of the legal acts of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine regarding the topics of our study is that they establish the foundations, requirements and procedures for making managerial decisions by the heads of units of the National Police.

3. An internal normative base that regulates the adoption of managerial decisions by managers

The Ministry of Internal Affairs is developing draft state programs on issues of public security and order, crime prevention, road safety, border guard, protection of objects and territories in the event of emergencies, as well as on migration issues. The orders of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, adopted within the powers envisaged by the law, are mandatory for execution by central executive authorities, their territorial bodies, local state administrations, authorities of the Autonomous Republic of Crimea, local

self-government bodies, enterprises, institutions and organizations irrespective of the form of ownership and citizens. , including the National Police of Ukraine when making managerial decisions by managers.

Therefore, the following orders of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine and the National Police of Ukraine should be noted, which should be taken into account when making managerial decisions by their leaders: the Regulations on the procedure for dealing with appeals of citizens and organization of their personal reception in the system of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine dated 10.10.2004; Instruction on the organization of the work of duty units and units of internal affairs of Ukraine, aimed at protecting the interests of society and the state from unlawful encroachments, dated April 29, 2009; Regulations on the patrol service of the Ministry of Internal Affairs dated 07.07.2015; Regulations on the Department of Patrol Police dated November 6, 2015; Regulations on the Department of Criminal Investigation of the National Police of Ukraine dated November 14, 2015; Instruction on registration of materials on administrative violations in the police authorities from 06.11.2015; Instruction on registration of police materials on administrative violations in the field of ensuring road safety, recorded not in automatic mode, from 07.11.2015; Instruction on the procedure for detecting signs of alcohol, narcotic or other intoxication or staying under the influence of drugs that reduce the attention and reaction speed of drivers from vehicles from 09.11.2015; Instruction on the organization of control over the execution of documents in the National Police of Ukraine from June 13, 2016; Instruction on automated accounting of administrative offenses from 04.07.2016; The order of the organization of the interaction of the National Guard of Ukraine and the National Police of Ukraine during the provision (protection) of public (public) security and order of 10.08.2016 (Administrative Activities of the Police in Questions and Answers, 2017, p. 19).

Individual acts are common in the practice of state-management activities, since they correspond most to its executive purpose and are the most important means of operational solution of current management issues (Neugendnikov, 2009, p. 205). Individual acts reflect the legal norms taking into account the specific situation and the actual specificity of the legal situation. The main requirement for individual acts is their strict compliance with legal acts, which establishes all the specifics of management of units of the National Police. The main thing in these acts is the concreteness, that is, the resolution through their help of individual cases and issues concerning specific individuals, the emergence of personalized administrative legal relationships, caused by these acts (Administrative Law of Ukraine, Academic course, 2004, p. 95). The most striking examples of acts of individual action are legal acts on personnel issues taken by heads of units of the National Police to establish an unimpeded process for the performance of police duties (for example, orders for appointment and dismissal), disciplinary measures to employees of these actors, decision on the interaction between individual organs and police units, etc.

They usually relate to one person or are limited by certain features of the circle of individuals and are aimed at resolving clearly defined issues.

Particular attention deserves the procedure for the adoption of individual legal acts that occupy a significant part of the entire array of legal acts of the National Police of Ukraine. These are the acts that reflect mainly in-house activities.

Individual legal acts have the following characteristics:

- Individual character, since it resolves very specific questions and specifies the specific addressee who must adhere to or is concerned with the order contained in the act;
- has a state-power character for those to whom it is addressed;
- is always issued unilaterally;
- causes the emergence, change, termination of administrative legal relations, that is, it is a legal fact (Salmanova, 2016, pp. 312-313).

In addition, distinguish the following signs of individual acts:

1) the subject of the adoption of individual administrative acts is the public administration, that is, the executive authorities, local self-government bodies, as well as other entities authorized by law;

2) individual administrative acts are decisions of public administration, that is, contain the will of the authorized entity;

3) individual administrative acts are unilateral decisions of the public administration, the addressees of such acts have the right to influence the content of the decision, but the final decision is always taken by the public administration;

4) individual administrative acts are authoritative decisions of public administration, which entails legal consequences for certain individuals or legal entities. Documents drawn up by the public administration in the course of adopting an individual administrative act, but not involving legal consequences (for example, an act of inspection or a protocol), do not belong to individual administrative acts;

5) individual administrative acts determine specific legal relations and concern specific individuals and legal entities;

6) under individual administrative acts, we understand only acts of external action, and internal administrative acts that define the legal relationship within the system of public administration bodies are a separate category;

7) individual administrative acts are usually taken in writing, however, in cases provided for by law, may be adopted either verbally or in conciliation;

8) due to the insufficient systemic development of administrative legislation, the names of the individual administrative act are different (orders, permissions, licenses, decisions-reports, etc.), determined by the laws, depending on the subject of acceptance or the sphere of legal relations. Thus, an individual administrative act is a generic term that covers the various names of acts;

9) individual administrative acts should be taken in strict accordance with the procedure established by law. As of today, the procedure for the adoption of such acts in Ukraine is not systematized and to a certain extent regulated only in special and legislative legislative, as well as, unfortunately, in by-laws (Salmanov, 2016, pp. 313-314).

The procedure for the adoption of individual legal acts differs from the general procedure for the publication of legal acts. In this case, it is possible to distinguish two of its types depending on the content of the act, namely:

- proceedings on the realization by citizens of their rights and responsibilities in the field of public administration;

- proceedings on the adoption of individual legal acts in the field of internal management of the subject of authority.

In the first case, the procedure includes the following steps:

- submission by citizens of the relevant application and its acceptance for consideration by the authorized entity;

- case review, analysis and selection for the application of relevant legal rules;

- decision making;
- execution of the decision;
- appeal or protest decision (Salmanova, 2016, pp. 314-315).

In the field of internal management, the initiator of the adoption of an individual legal act is a competent official. Reasons for making such a decision may be rules of law, events that have legal consequences, or other circumstances that led to the need for such an act. The proceeding begins with an analysis of the situation or the rules of law. Then, the legal rules on which the legal act will be based will be chosen and a corresponding decision is made, which will be issued in the established order. The decision taken may be challenged or challenged by the person concerned. The receipt of complaints does not stop the execution of the decision, which must be executed immediately or in accordance with the terms specified by the individual legal act.

Adoption of an individual act of management in one person's manner is carried out by its signing by an appropriate official. Possible and collegiate order of adoption of an individual management act. Such an arrangement involves discussing an act that is adopted and conducting a vote on its adoption.

Thus, the adoption of legal acts of the National Police of Ukraine is conditioned by the specifics of its work and differs depending on the type of legal act. To date, in this body of state power there is no normative legal act that would regulate this procedure, which negatively affects the quality of legal acts and the procedure for implementing the procedure for their adoption. In such an act it is necessary to consolidate the procedure of approval, discussion, registration, publication of legal acts and bringing them to the notice of performers, based on the division of legal acts into general and individual ones (Salmanova, 2016, p. 315).

We share the point of view of VV Konoplyov, who in his dissertation explores the following tasks of legal support for the adoption of managerial decisions by managers, and we believe that they are relevant to the departments of the National Police:

- ensuring the exact distribution of competences (rights and responsibilities) between the units (officials, individual employees) of the police;
- rationalization of the construction of a system for the adoption of managerial decisions and accurate correlation with the institution of responsibility;
- ordering the distribution of time required for the preparation, adoption and execution of management decisions;
- Personnel, information, financial and logistical support for the preparation, adoption and execution of management decisions;
- definition of criteria of efficiency of administrative decisions;
- providing a system of supervisory and supervisory activities for making managerial decisions in law enforcement activities of the units of the National Police of Ukraine (Konoplyov, 2006, p. 114).

Hence it follows that the essence of legal support for the adoption of managerial decisions by heads in the units of the National Police is as follows:

- 1) the legal consolidation of tasks, competencies, functions, organizational structure of all units of the police;
- 2) normative determination of the forms, methods and techniques of the most effective foreign-administrative and internal-organizational activities of the police;
- 3) the details of social relations, which are regulated by normative acts of higher legal force.

The competence for the preparation and adoption of managerial decisions by the heads in the units of the National Police of Ukraine is determined by the place of the head in the hierarchical system of the police. The higher the rank is taken by the head, the broader his competence and the higher legal force are his managerial decisions (Konoplyov, 2006, pp. 114-115).

The preparation and adoption of legal acts by heads of units of the National Police of Ukraine consists of a set of successive actions, which are united in the appropriate stages of the proceedings. To date, there is no single view on the number and content of the stages of rule-making proceedings. However, after analyzing the scientific views at the stage of the rule-making process and taking into account the specifics of the legal acts of the National Police of Ukraine, let us dwell on the point of view of O. Y. Salmanova concerning the stages of adoption of legal acts:

- 1) identification of needs and planning of preparation and publication of legal acts;
- 2) drafting a legal act;
- 3) promulgation and discussion of the draft legal act;
- 4) consideration and adoption of a legal act;
- 5) registration of a legal act;
- 6) the official publication of the legal act and its application to execution.

Each of these steps includes a number of stages and management actions. Their totality and order differ depending on the type of legal act, its contents and the range of persons to whom its action applies. At the same time, there are a number of general rules that the procedure for adopting legal acts must comply with (Salmanov, 2016, pp. 260, 263-264).

To date, the legislation lacks a clear list of legal acts that may be issued by the National Police of Ukraine. Their species are found on the list of powers of the head of the police, which states that he:

- signs the orders of the police;
- abolishes, in full or in a separate part of acts of territorial police bodies;
- within the limits of the authority, issues orders that are mandatory for police officers, civil servants and police officers;
- approves the provisions on independent structural units of the police apparatus.

That is, orders, orders and regulations are used in the activity of the police. This list is not exhaustive, since in practice there are such legal acts as instructions, instructions, statutes, decisions, etc. (Salmanova, 2016, pp. 285).

Summing up, I would like to note that the legal framework for the adoption of managerial decisions by heads in the departments of the National Police of Ukraine is provided by a large number of various normative acts. As G.V. Atamanchuk notes, in order to achieve the optimal structure of legal provision of public administration, the process of establishing rights should be systematically organized. It is important to achieve interaction: by the time the publication of legal acts; in the content of the norms governing the same type of relations; for bodies that make up subsystems of public administration; by the legal force of legal acts belonging to one level of the organizational structure of governance (Atamanchuk, 2000, pp. 179). The same applies to the legal provision of the preparation and adoption of managerial decisions by heads in police units, the norms of which should be coordinated (coordinated) by the legal force, the bodies issuing them, as well as the time and content of their regulations.

Conclusions.

In order to increase the effectiveness of law enforcement activities, the heads of the National Police units who take legal management decisions, that is, those that entail certain legal consequences, must take into account the following:

1. The system of normative legal acts that form the basis of legal support for the preparation and adoption of managerial decisions by heads in the units of the National Police of Ukraine can be divided into two groups: external - those that exist outside the scope of the police, and internal - covered by the competence of the police.

2. Legal support for the adoption of management decisions by the heads of the departments of the National Police of Ukraine contains normative acts that stipulate certain requirements for the procedure for the preparation and adoption of management decisions, their contents, registration, etc.; is the reason or condition for the adoption of appropriate managerial decisions in the police.

3. To achieve the effectiveness of legal support for the adoption of managerial decisions by the heads of the units of the National Police of Ukraine can be provided that the requirements of legal acts on legal consolidation are harmonized:

1) the competence of managers to make managerial decisions on certain issues of the foreign-administrative or internal-organizational activities of the police;

2) the content of managerial decisions;

3) the order of their preparation and acceptance, legal technique of registration;

4) the system of entities that are authorized to exercise control and oversight responsibilities for the implementation of management decisions.

4. The work on making managerial decisions requires the heads of the departments of the National Police of Ukraine to have a high level of competence, time, energy, experience. It also provides for a high level of responsibility, since in order to implement the decisions made, it is necessary to ensure an efficient and coordinated work for the entire unit. Therefore, understanding the peculiarities of legal support for making managerial decisions is extremely important for all managers who want to ensure a high level of efficiency of their activities and activities of the unit as a whole.

5. Preparation and adoption of legal acts by the National Police is one of the main procedures in the executive and regulatory activities of its leaders. The development and implementation of legal acts is intended to ensure the proper implementation of the current legislation in the activities of the police, to determine the peculiarities of the implementation of legal norms and to improve the effectiveness of law enforcement activities. It is from the proper implementation of this procedure, the observance of all rules and techniques depends on the accuracy and quality of the tasks performed by the police.

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